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DNA methylation is intrinsically linked with Xist activation.

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In these studies, chemical inhibition of DNA methyltransferases with 5-azacytidine, which resulted in activation of Xist, was utilized to demonstrate control of Xist activation by DNA methylation. This was accompanied by loss of Tet1 expression and marked reduction of Poli, a DNA polymerase functioning in translesion repair.